

DATA WAREHOUSE APPLICATIONS: A COMPREHENSIVE SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: of Data warehouse in different Application Areas

Design / Methodology: More than 60 articles have been studied in the field of data warehouse with different keywords as applications of data warehouse, architecture of data warehouse and usage of data warehouse. The articles are searched from Google scholar search engine. Textual search is carried out to figure out the results.

Findings: Data Warehouse has provided a great support in many organizations by managing data from different sources. It structures information and helps organization in taking effective and efficient decisions.

Practical Implications: It is highly used technology as with the introduction of big data huge amount of information is generated on the daily basis and also data warehouse presents the information in highly organized, clean and integrated form as per the need of time. Organizations have huge amount of information and also all data is in different formats but it is difficult to take decision as it is not in the organized form and data warehouse helps in providing quality data which helps all organizations to further progress. All organizations either government or non-government can get benefit from it.

Originality/ Value: Study of different authors research work done by them is analyzed in a detailed level relevant to our usage of data warehouse and its applications. Information generated in the paper is highly accurate and reliable.

Keywords: Data warehouse, Decision Making, Information, Knowledge base, Architecture

Paper Type: Review Paper

INTRODUCTION

Data Warehouse is one of the processes which is used for collecting and managing heterogeneous information from different sources. It helps in providing deeper insights into

the business. It is requisite for all information and business-oriented industries. Data warehouse has its origin since 1980s and is still used widely. It is store house of information. It has steadfast hardware and software that helps in extracting information through implementations of algorithms (Rasheed Umair et al. (2014)). It is always subject oriented, time -variable, and continuous collection of data (Gosaina Anjana et al. (2015)).

In today's competitive world huge amount of information is generated every day from different sources. So, there is a need to organize this huge amount of information for meaningful use. Invariability in the data leads to difficulty in analyzing results and quality has to be compromised in many cases. Data warehouse is a fusion of technology and different components which helps at different perspectives in taking better strategic decisions. In today's era there is exponential growth in data and if this huge volume of data is to be managed the only solution is data warehouse. Data warehouse provides place where information can be easily combined and stored. It allows proper maintenance of data as new information can be added and existing information can be changed when required. The demand for Data Warehouse has been continuously increasing from 2003 to 2015 as it is recorded as \$3.5 billion to \$15.5 billion and this indicates dependency of organizations on Data Warehouse (Xiaobing Yu (2021)).

Data warehouse is a database that helps organizations to enhance their performance. It is usually a historical data that is derived from transactional data. This analysis of data gives better understanding for the business in decision taking. The data in data warehouse is loaded through the process of extraction, transformation and loading from heterogeneous sources. The two main terms associated with data warehouse are data mart and operational data. Data mart has limited scope as it serves only a particular department but has faster creation as it has limited coverage. Operational database is useful for supporting daily operations as it is based on current data. The data stored in data warehouse is in organized, polished and standardized form which forms the bedrock for business intelligence (Ahmad Hassan (2021)). The craves and large need of information has given rise to the need of data warehouse so that information can be attained in a timely manner and organized form.

Data warehouse updating can be done in a conventional or in real time. The limitations of conventional method in updating the contents have given rise to the real time approach. The main usage of real time methods is availability of updated information immediately which helps in taking quick decisions and immediately handling of problems. Real time data warehouses store and format the data as soon as data is generated. (Bouaziz Senda et al. (2017)).

Now-a-days importance of data warehouse cannot be ignored due to number of benefits provided by it. Organizations take their major decisions depending on the accurate and reliable data which helps companies to take big challenges. In today's technical era all the devices are connected to the internet and exchange data. So, there is more need of data warehouse that makes it more powerful. In this paper we are going to discuss all those major areas in which data warehouse is highly used. It includes business, government sector, healthcare, industries, social media, education, banking and many more. It is difficult to manage the task in these areas without using techniques of data warehouse. As internet is

generating huge amount of information every day and data warehouse helps in storing and organizing information.

DATA WAREHOUSE

Data warehouse is a technique that collects data from varied sources so that useful business results could be derived from it. It supports analyzing capabilities and handling of structured queries so that better and deeper insights of business can be attained. It helps in taking better decisions which leads the business to success by facing different challenges. It involves the process of cleaning, integrating and consolidations of data.

ARCHITECTURE OF DATA WAREHOUSE

It is one of the ways for defining the complete structure of information processing system. It is used to define overall communication process and how information is presented to end-users within the organization. Generally, data warehouse embraces three tier approaches. These approaches are

- Top-tier
- Middle-tier
- Bottom-tier

Top-tier architecture- The very initial step in this approach is collecting of data from various sources, transformation and migration of data. The database is constructed from raw and historical data. (RizviAliSayed et al. (2021)). This layer comprises of different analysis and mining tools. This tier is the front-end client layer. This layer holds the query tools and reporting tools, analysis tools and data mining tools.

Figure1: Top-tier architecture

1. Middle-tier architecture- In this data is transformed into a structure that is more suitable for analysis and queries. It is done with the help of relational and multidimensional OLAP.

2. Bottom-Tier architecture-It is the database which includes clean and formatted data. In its data marts are created which are provided to the users for quick analyzing and reporting (RizviAliSayed et al. (2021).

Figure2: Bottom-Tier Architecture

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This paper is built on the certainty derived from randomly selected journals in the area of data warehouse. At the initial levels only abstract analysis of papers has been done to verify its relevance to data warehouse. More than 60 articles have been studied in the field of data warehouse with different keywords as applications of data warehouse, architecture of data warehouse and usage of data warehouse. The articles are searched from Google scholar search engine. Out of these papers 43 were studied in complete detail according to the relevance of topic. Textual search is carried out to figure out the results. Related work is mainly carried out to study different application areas in which data warehouse is used. It is highly used technology as with the introduction of big data huge amount of information is generated on the daily basis and also data warehouse presents the information in highly organized, clean and integrated form as per the need of time. Organizations have huge amount of information and also all data is in different formats but it is difficult to take decision as it is not in the organized form and data warehouse helps in providing quality data which helps all organizations to further progress. Information generated in the paper is highly accurate and reliable. All organizations either government or non-government can get benefit from it.

Study of different authors research work done by them is analyzed in a detailed level relevant to our usage of data warehouse and its applications. The author of the papers described about quality of data warehouse is very crucial as all organizations depend completely on the data. All the fields success depends on quality of data contained in it (GosainaAnjana et al. (2015)). The author in this paper discussed about decision can be taken faster if information is available in precise, clean and standardized format which is possible only if data cleaning algorithms are used. The paper describes about the application of data

warehouse that is clinical review which discuss about human lives importance and for saving them right decision should be taken which is related to information gathered from heterogeneous sources and data warehouse helps in managing all clinical or health related data (HamoudkhalafAlaaAlaaet al. (2018).

The author (RizviAliSayed et al. (2021) also discusses about the importance of data warehouse and also about ETL processing which is a significant layer in taking decisions in an organization. The paper also discusses about transmission of historical data and the current data to data warehouse. The author in this paper signifies as how fast arising data that is Big Data is handled by data warehouse by using different innovative tools and methods. The author also discusses about changes to be made in architecture of data warehouse for handling Big Data (SolodovnikovaDarjaet al. (2021).The author (GuptaAbhishek et al. (2020) describes about important role a data warehouse in business corporations in decision making.

The author in his paper describes importance of data warehouse in Project Management. Project managers in order to fulfill their tasks are always abiding by the constraints of time, complexity, size and cost. To achieve success in their projects, project managers had to rely on previous knowledge and then represent their findings which are possible only through data warehouse (BogojevicPetar (2020).

The author (Xiaobing Yu (2021) suggested introducing data warehouse in the field of educational institutions. As number of colleges and universities are increasing the management of information will be difficult. So, for betterment in taking decisions educational institutions have to opt data warehouse. The author (Pramudianto Ferry et al. (2016) here describes importance of data warehouse in peer assessment at education level.As students generate millions of views by giving and receiving feedback to each other. The author also focused on rating system for peer assessment.

The author (Pablo C. de Albuquerque et al. (2021) in this paper describes how data warehouse helps in solving the problems of educational institution by integrating data from different sources, normalizing the database and answering of all data queries relating to administrative, technical and public. The author (Shahid Bilal Muhammad et al. (2016) herediscusses the importance of data warehouse in real life applications.The author also further describes that data warehouse is more preferable in non-government organizations than government organizations. The technology is used in almost every domain of real life for quick decisions.

The author (ChaudharySachin et al. (2011) described usage of data warehouse in decision making. The author also discussed about the availability of technical tools and different architectures that supports decision making. The author (MoallaImenet et al. (2017)discussed the importance of data warehouse in social media. As most of the users interact through social media by giving their views on different products, services which further helps in taking decisions on different projects. The different approaches in data warehouse helps in simplifying the task.

The author (Koshiya B Kruti (2017) highlights that technology of data warehouse and online analytical processing has done a lot in taking timelystrategic decisions which are

essential for today's marketing trend. The author (JhaRohini (2020) in this paper depicts that government has to manage huge amount of information of its citizens. But unstructured decision is more problematic so data warehouse and data mining methods helps to manage it efficiently. The author (HassanAhmad (2021) specifies how data warehouse acts as a central hub for maintainingintegrated information. It helps a lot in all application areas where there is difficulty in managing complex data. Decision making system made a lot of improvements with its help.

Table 1: Related studies

S. No	Name of The Author	Year	Title	Remarks
1.	PornpitWongthongtham, Bilal Abu Salih	2015	Ontology and Trust based Data Warehouse in New Generation of Business Intelligence State-of-the-art, challenges, and opportunities	Data Warehouse helps all corporate sector and business make success on the basis of their right decisions.
2.	Ahmad Hassan	2021	Review of industries need to depend on data warehouse for decision making and taking benefit from it.	Data warehouse is required in different organizations for extracting knowledge from large databases.
3.	AbhishekDabas , VandanaDabass , Heena Mehta	2013	Impact of Data Warehouse in Decision Making Process	Managers have to take coherent decisions by considering different data mining solutions, feedback and by considering viable alternatives.
4.	Nur Hani ZulkifliAbaia, ,Jamaiah H. Yahayab , Aziz Deraman	2013	User Requirement Analysis in Data Warehouse Design: A Review	. Data warehouse is embedded with all such tools that assist in decision making. As data is extracted from various sources there is a possibility of errors in it so data warehouse clean and scrutinize all data before loading into it
5.	DarjaSolodovnikova and LailaNiedrite	2018	Towards a Data Warehouse Architecture for Managing Big Data Evolution	Architecture of data warehouse permits to perform different online analytical processing tasks and also proposes changes to data as per user's requirements
6.	Prof. Kruti B Koshiya	2017	Review on Data Warehouse: As Prerequisite Aspect of Business Decision Making Activity	It helps in providing different architectures so that information can be arranged as per business requirements. The information gathered from different sources and also in different formats can be organized at a single repository so that better decisions can be taken.

7.	Luciano Moraes da Luz Brum et al.	2019	Business Intelligence and Data Warehouse in Agrarian Sector: A Bibliometric Study	Availability of different visualizing tools, ad-hoc queries, online analytical processing leads to the enhancements in strategic decisions
8.	Leo Willyanto Santos o, Yulia	2017	Data Warehouse with Big Data Technology for Higher Education	Universities and higher education systems are going through competitive environment in which they have to manage huge amount of information in order to handle all social, political and economic changes. This information should be handled in a timely manner for real decisions
9.	Ferry Pramudianto et al.	2016	Peer Review Data Warehouse: Insights from Different Systems	Educational institutions need data warehouse for peer assessment. Assessment structure can be improved continuously by feedback system which is sent and also received from students
10.	Jane R. Schubart et al.	2000	Evaluation of a Data Warehouse in an Academic Health Sciences Center	Data warehouse has helped a lot in linking of old system to different departmental systems. It has done a lot in improving the quality of a system by providing relevant details. The diffusion of information has given right and timely assessment of records along with practical dispersion.
11.	AlaaAlaaKhalaf Hamoud et al.	2018	Clinical Data Warehouse: A Review	It is used to link all patients personal record which includes medicinal treatment, diagnosis, physician's comments. Incorrect information can find to provide very harmful effects rather than providing any support. So, quality of information matters a lot.
12.	Christina Khnaisser et al.	2015	Data Warehouse Design Methods Review for the Healthcare Domain	Clinical data warehouse should be flexible enough to make changes as information need to be re-considered after certain time period
13.	MARY F. WISNIEWSKI et al.	2003	Development of a Clinical Data Warehouse for Hospital Infection Control	Stored data of medical organizations helps to enhance performance and also improves care quality.
14.	AdiFirmanRama dhan et al.	2021	Data governance and its scientific outlook in Indonesia: a literature review	The policies and all the procedures used for managing the government data or other organization data must ensure reliability, quality, security, consistency and approachability of

				data whenever it is required. It should solve all the compound problems of the government.
15.	AzizahBt Haji Ahmad et al.	2016	From Data Warehouse To Big Data: E-Government Initiatives	Government manages all these data through information and communication technology which is benefitting many non-government organizations, other agencies, businesses, employees and general public.
16.	DrRohiniJha	2020	Review of Data Mining and Data Warehousing Implementation in E-Governance	. Data warehouse has enhanced reliability and quality in government policies and setting of native governments also has enhanced through it.
17.	Vuong M. Ngo et al.	2018	An Efficient Data Warehouse for Crop Yield Prediction	Precision agriculture is one of the areas which helps in taking better decisions by providing access to all the stakeholders which are associated with farming and also maintaining the privacy, security and confidentiality of the stored information.
18.	Andrew Kusiak	2006	Data Mining in Manufacturing: A Review	Every step-in manufacturing industry from purchasing of raw material, maintaining of inventory level, designing, maintenance and to the sale of product is depended on efficient management of information. This efficient management of knowledge helps in making predictions for many further applications.
19.	K.W. Chau et al.	2002	Application of Data Warehouse and Decision Support System in Construction Management	It provides time variant information which can be very helpful for long-term and short-term decision making. It helps construction company to convert routine operational activities into tactical decisions which is very useful for managers.
20.	ImenMoalla et al.	2017	Data warehouse design approaches from social media: review and comparison	Data warehouse has proven to be very helpful in easy managing of large information through OLAP cubes. Information can be viewed from different perspectives through these analytical cubes and gives new dimensions for handling this unmanaged information.
21.	Wei Xu	2020	Analyzing social	. It helps in getting deeper insights

			media data and performance comparison with traditional database, data warehouse, and MapReduce approaches	of all sales, purchase, marketing and all business elements in the form of tables.it does all the analysis at different levels of city, state and country level. Data warehouse helps in attaining very precise and accurate results so that data can move in a right track without any deviation.
22.	C.AmaliPushpa m et al.	2017	Overview on Data Mining in Social Media	Data collected in data warehouse is analyzed to determine patterns and their relationships. Different organizations make different plans and strategies according to the opinions of the buyers.
23.	Marta Nave et al.	2018	A Decision Support System Framework to Track Consumer Sentiments in Social Media	Different experiences of the users help in knowing different places of visit through social media. Data warehouse helps in storing all such opinions which will benefit all the tourism industry in creating strong databases.
24.	Kauppi, K., Moxham, C., & Bamford, D.	2013	Should we try out for the major leagues? A call for research in sport operations management.	Data regarding different sports is integrated from different sources, extracted and gets loaded into data warehouse for deeper understandings of sports and its dash board. It further helps in reliable decisions as organization of data leads to effective results.
25.	LIU Yan, LIU Xiaofang	2015	The Research on Sports Training Aids System Based on Data Warehouse Technology	Data warehouse helps in extracting information for the users to take decisions from the current environment by applying data mining techniques. Relational model of data warehouse helps in representing information in star scheme and fact tables for quicker decisions and deeper analysis.
26.	EstiyanDwipriy oko et al.	2021	Wireless Scoreboard Technology Architecture for Athlete Performance Data Warehouse at Multiple Table Sports Games	It guides the coaches to figure out strategies and tactics for training their wards. It is of great assistance for analyzers to take decisions. The statistics are easily generated according to the performance level of sportsperson and also provides digitized for keeping records of tournament.
27.	Dr. Beate List et al.	2002	Extending the Data Warehouse with	Banks need data warehouse to maintain information at a central

			Company External Data from Competitors' Websites: A Case Study in the Banking Sector	core and helps management in taking decisions. It is one of the modern ways to measure the performance of organizations.
28.	SemihOnut et al.	2002	Customer Relationship Management in Banking Sector and A Model Design for Banking Performance Enhancement	Data warehouse has helped a lot in managing customer relationships in banks. It helps in providing customer's geographic information, transactions committed and status of profitability relationship.
29.	G. KoteswaraRao et al.	2011	Framework to integrate business intelligence and knowledge management in banking industry	Business intelligence on the data warehouse helps managers of all levels to take effective decisions. This strong knowledge of databases helps banks to survive easily in competitive environment.
30.	AruneeIntrapair ot et al.	2014	Adoption and diffusion of data warehousing technology: a system dynamics approach	Banking sector is trying to remove all hindrances like technology limitation, staff effectiveness, vendor support so that it should be adopted with full advantage.

APPLICATION OF DATA WAREHOUSE

The importance of data warehouse cannot be challenged as it is used in almost all the fields. As the complexity of data increases along with its size it is difficult to manage the data. So, to provide solution to it we have to depend on data warehouse. There are many domains in which importance of data warehouse cannot be refused. Some of the application areas are discussed in which it is widely used.

Business Management: Data warehouse tools are very valuable in today's competitive world. It helps in providing different architectures so that information can be arranged as per business requirements. The information gathered from different sources and also in different formats can be organized at a single repository so that better decisions can be taken (Koshiya B Kruti (2017)). Data warehouse helps in extraction, transformation and loading of information called ETL process facilitate better understanding of concept and useful decisions for the progress of business. Availability of different visualizing tools, ad-hoc queries, online analytical processing leads to the enhancements in strategic decisions. Data warehouse handles organization's absolute data and from its business data is extracted for decisions. It modernizes the whole data through better business analytical tools. Data for data warehouse is derived from historical and current data. Data warehouse provides many benefits to business. Some of them are:

- Fast access to data- As data is gathered from different sources is all put together which helps business in fast accessing of information. It is must in today's competitive world for quick decisions.
- Quality and consistency of data- Data is stored in standardized format which leads towards more accuracy. Confidence in quality of data gets build up as it is up-to date and more reliable which is must for business decisions.
- Finer decisions- Businesses are no longer based on limited data. Data warehouse has loads of data facts and information statistics which lead to better decisions in different segments like marketing, finance, sales and inventory.
- Better customer relationship management- As it maintains the information at a single site it helps in deriving accurate and true results which is must for maintaining customers.

Figure 3: Integrated approach of business Intelligence and Data Warehouse

Source: <http://www.metsistem.com/images/Data-warehousing.png>

- Data warehouse handles all business data decisions with accuracy and timeliness. Gigabytes of data is stored and transactions are processed at a very fast rate so updating of database is also must so that its value could be maintained (RasheedUmair et al. (2014). To meet the needs of strategic requirements management of knowledge is must. Business should unite with knowledge management system in order to improve its performance. It gives advantage to the clients and business efficiency get rises with it as it creates, stores, processes and refine all the knowledge (D. Ahmed; et al., 2021). Data warehouse helped a lot in predicting the future based on previous data. Return on investments in business get improved as it almost handles 99% of queries immediately resulting in satisfaction of customers (HassanAhmad (2021).

Decision Making: Data warehouse helps in providing deeper insights into the database by transforming data into information. This useful information is based on the historical and current data which is more precise, accurate and reliable. All corporate sector and business make success on the basis of their right decisions. As per report generated by International Data Corporation (IDC), organizations carries 80% of data is in unstructured form and it is

increasing every year. This data is generated continuously from social media, web blogs, news agencies and many other sources (Wongthongtham P. et al. (2015).

Now decisions are based on important facts and figures and decisions makers does not have to rely on limited data. The database of business contains data from various sources such as sales, finance, marketing and various other businesses. This also has fueled decision support system. Data warehouse allows availability of long-drawn-out information for the corporate sector to assist them in taking better strategic decisions. Processed data helps in viewing information from different perspectives and allows for smarter decisions (HassanAhmad (2021).

Users prefer information sharing only when it is prompt, coherent and reliable. But organizations have many different types of databases so there is a need of some coordination among these databases which is possible only with data warehouse. It helps to generate models, statistical analysis, reporting for wise decisions. Managers have to take coherent decisions at every step but it is possible only if important problems are prioritizing and then solved by considering different data mining solutions, feedback and by considering viable alternatives (DabasAbhisheket al. (2013). Data warehouse helps decision makers in:

- It helps decision makers to take decisions from large amount of data.
- It helps to identify hidden patterns for decisions.
- It helps to attain information from heterogeneous sources and customize it for reliable and consistent decisions.
- It allows decision makers to view the information in the form of charts, grids and reports for systematic decisions.

There is a great explosion in the development of number of services that are related to data warehouse. All different companies related to health, education, manufacturing, transport, retail etc. are based on information system. Data warehouse is embedded with all such tools that assist in decision making. As data is extracted from various sources there is a possibility of errors in it so data warehouse clean and scrutinize all data before loading into it (Nur Hani ZulkifliAbaiet al. (2013). Architecture of data warehouse permits to perform different online analytical processing tasks and also proposes changes to data as per user's requirements (Solodovnikova D et al. (2021).

Data warehouse and ETL performs important role in refining decisions. ETL is one of the important layers in data warehouse which supports important decisions. In today's competitive era smarter decisions are needed within short span of time for the success of business (Rizvi Ali Sayedet al. (2021).

Figure 4: Data Warehouse Decision Making Process

Source: <https://www.javatpoint.com/data-warehouse-architecture>

Education: Data warehouse plays an important role in the field of education. It is beneficial both for students and teachers. It helps in improving both teaching and learning. The extraction of information from a single source is never sufficient so it is collected from various heterogeneous sources; synthesized, assessed, summarized and useful results are drawn from it. Data warehouse assists in analyzing all the problems in this era and provides solution for it.

Universities and higher education systems are going through competitive environment in which they have to manage huge amount of information in order to handle all social, political and economic changes. This information should be handled in a timely manner for real decisions. Different tools, techniques and algorithms are used for analyzing and processing of the huge amount of information collected. The top management has different dashboards for monitoring all the institutions performance under their universities at global level (Santoso Willyanto Leo et al. (2017)). Educational institutions need data warehouse for peer assessment. Assessment structure can be improved continuously by feedback system which is sent and also received from students. The huge amount of information is managed by data warehouse in the form of fact and dimension tables. Results are derived from this huge amount of information for assessing the performance of students by ranking and rating (Pramudianto Ferry et al. (2016)).

As data warehouse deals with very precious information so it must be handled very carefully. It contains repository of many institutions which is stored and organized. To access this valuable information DW uses multidimensional structure. It deals with all aspects like availability of courses, students registered, faculty, infrastructure, academic achievements and many more. All these are represented in an effective way so that better conclusions can be reached (Mirabedini Shirin (2014)). Some of interesting reasons of why educational institutions prefer data warehouse are

- Easy Assessment- It provides all the assessment Performa at a single place. It helps in assessing institution performance and can also provide comparative study with other institution in a state. Its main attention is analysis of performance.
- Availability of right information – It allows to access the information as per user interest. Need for information is different for principal, teachers, students and clerical staff. So, one can view it as per their need and requirements.
- Timely availability- It allows to access the information every time whenever it is required and also provides up to date data as it is must for effective decisions.
- Fast Tendency- A well-structured database helps to focus on the required information. It uses color coding, summaries, charts and reports so that top level authorities are able to reach on conclusions by focusing on suitable trends.
- Get rid of spreadsheets- It eliminates the need of preparing spreadsheets for each and every task and then sharing with each other which leads to huge cumbersome task and lot of redundancy. But now focus is on learning and teaching.

Figure5: Data Warehouse

Educational institutions can also use data warehouse for uploading author's task. It should be loaded on the portal. The number of research articles, books, journals and all research related task is stored and assessed at a single repository. The number and volumes of all such articles can be assessed and evaluated by the evaluators (Pablo C. et al. (2021).

Data warehouse helps in providing strong environment for teachers and learners. It helps in managing all the students of educational institution from a single platform. It assists in assessing student performance and remarks are assigned by the teachers which helps in students improvement. It also assures protection of data by various security measures (Goyal Monika et al. (2012).

Health: Data Warehouse has made it possible for many companies to make powerful decisions based on data-driven approach. It has provided success to many industries. One of them is healthcare industries. It has improved efficiency as record maintained for years helps in improved customer satisfaction and also leads to improvement in operational tasks. Data warehouse has helped a lot in linking of old system to different departmental systems. It has done a lot in improving the quality of a system by providing relevant details. The diffusion of information has given right and timely assessment of records along with practical dispersion.

IMPORTANCE OF DATA WAREHOUSE IN HEALTH SCIENCES

- Effective decisions
- Better treatment
- Better degree of care
- Better and enhanced management of resources

As there are number of medical institutions which tries to provide best services to their patients so all these institutions are moving toward building clinical data warehouses for best decisions. It is used to link all patients' personal record which includes medicinal treatment, diagnosis, and physician's comments. Incorrect information can find to provide very harmful effects rather than providing any support. So, quality of information matters a lot. The success of system depends upon all such tools, hardware, researchers and organization data that helps in managing data in a secured manner so that operational and strategic decisions are handled properly (Hamoud khalaf Alaa Alaa et al. (2018).

Stored data of medical organizations helps to enhance performance and also improves care quality. The data extracted from different hospitals helps to identify their methods, problems different administrators are facing in their hospitals. It also helps in controlling any infectious diseases as number of cases of that particular infectious disease. Results can be derived with precision as data is driven from reliable sources and it helps in identifying time and money spent on preventing it (Wisniewski F Mary et al. (2003).

Government: Large amount of information is gathered and maintained by government since last years. In order to manage all valuable information, there is need of data warehouse. Huge amount of gathered information helps to reveal all the hidden patterns so that right decisions are taken at right time. It also helps to solve all ad-hoc queries also to provide valuable insights of data so that structured reports could be generated which would leads to the right goal.

The policies and all the procedures used for managing the government data or other organization data must ensure reliability, quality, security, consistency and approachability of data whenever it is required. It should solve all the compound problems of the government

(Ramadhan, A. F et al.(2021).Government has to take all the strategic decisions regarding setting of policies, procedures, financial statements on the basis of which other organizations has to take decisions. Data warehousing helps to achieve it through analytics and ingenious ways.

Figure6: Data Warehouse Areas in Government Sector

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Government-Application-of-Data-Warehouse_fig5_301770422

Now -a-days governments are relying on internet and web-based technology for quicker and efficient decisions. Government manages all these data through information and communication technology which is benefitting many non-government organizations, other agencies, businesses, employees and general public (Ahmad Haji BtAzizah et al. (2016).

Benefits of Data Warehouse in Government: The field of Government has benefitted a lot from data warehouse. It includes

- Sharing of information with different organizations.

- Financial and budgeting can be handled easily by the government.
- Tax collection becomes easier.
- Payment of bills becomes easy.
- Suggestions, dissatisfaction and comments of public can be handled easily.
- Dissemination of information becomes easier.
- Better decision making by government.
- Online registration for different kinds of applications.
- Online handling of complaints and petitions.

India is a democratic country which has many levels of government substantiate from district levels to the national level. Huge amount of information is distributed among all these levels for its smooth functioning so that it acts a single governing body. Data warehouse model for central government is conducted which includes dissemination and collection of information from different administrative and statutory bodies without creating replica of information. The whole data is incorporated at a single place which helps to move towards wiser decisions and better policy enforcements can be imposed. Data warehouse has enhanced reliability and quality in government policies and setting of native governments also has enhanced through it (DrJhaRohini (2020)).

Manufacturing: Data warehousing is a multi-dimensional database which is used for building powerful database based on the data collected from different companies and reliable decisions are based on this gathered information. It helps industries in dealing with the problems of budgeting, scheduling and generation of high-level reports. Data warehouse also helps industries in efficient handling of all processes from purchasing, manufacturing and shipping of goods. Stored information of data warehouse helps in improving relationships with customers by providing customer satisfaction, flexibility in taking decisions and also helps in surviving efficiently in today's competitive edge.

Data warehouse helps in agriculture industry also. Common agricultural activities like crop yielding, management of crops, pesticides, temperature, humidity and many more are automated with the help of techniques of data warehouse. With the help of information and communication technologies farmers can share information and crops at a global level. Gathered information of large repository also helps farmers in making advance predictions of weather, droughts, floods and how to handle all such matters efficiently. Precision agriculture is one of the areas which helps in taking better decisions by providing access to all the stakeholders which are associated with farming and also maintaining the privacy, security and confidentiality of the stored information (Vuong M. Ngo et al. (2018)).

One of the most valuable aspects for the success of any organization is its knowledge base which is efficiently developed by data warehouse design by maintaining all the previous and current data. Every step-in manufacturing industry from purchasing of raw material, maintaining of inventory level, designing, maintenance and to the sale of product is depended on efficient management of information. This efficient management of knowledge helps in making predictions for many further applications (Kusiak Andrew (2006)).

The powerful features of data warehouse serve a lot in construction industry also. It provides time variant information which can be very helpful for long-term and short-term decision making. It helps Construction Company to convert routine operational activities into tactical decisions which is very useful for managers. It also assists in determining market trends, cost incurred in machinery, increase in number of employees, material intake and so on (Chau K.W. et al. (2002)).

Usage of Data Warehouse In Manufacturing

- Better Forecasting
- Determining business trends
- Determine customer needs
- Better product management
- Management of Inventory Level
- Management of plant capacity
- Determine Market Competitors
- Product management

Data warehouse helps organizations in providing visual representations so that better insights of data could be reached for efficient decisions. It assists in predicting stronger areas in business and manufacturing decisions are taken by determining all such market trends. Industries take operational and strategic decisions by analyzing historical trends and patterns (Ahmad Hassan (2021)).

Social Media: Social media is internet build technology that allows easy sharing of data, views, information at a worldwide level. It includes different platforms as Facebook, twitter, Instagram etc. The number of internet users are increasing day by day. Huge amount of information is generated through social sites everywhere which needs to be managed efficiently. Many research analysts have focused on doing competitive analysis of social media and to transform its information into knowledge which will help decision makers in taking right decisions. Social media has helped many organizations in taking strategic decisions. Social media contains lot of unstructured data which needs to be managed by some efficient platform. Data warehouse has proven to be very helpful in easy managing of large information through OLAP cubes. Information can be viewed from different perspectives through these analytical cubes and gives new dimensions for handling this unmanaged information (MoallaImen et al. (2017)).

The effective way of handling integrated information which is constituent of text, data, images, videos and many more data warehouse multidimensional model is preferred for analyzing unstructured information. Facts, dimensions and attributes are easily represented through this. It helps in getting deeper insights of all sales, purchase, marketing and all business elements in the form of tables. It does all the analysis at different levels of city, state and country level. Data warehouse helps in attaining very precise and accurate results so that data can move in a right track without any deviation (Xu, Wei (2020)).

Social media has become a good source for all users to share information at a reasonable cost. It helps them to express their views, opinions on any matter. It helps

different organizations, friends, relatives and all to come together to express their views and extract information. It has helped companies a lot in marketing their products through social media sites. It has helped companies to promote and increase the sale of goods and services at a reasonable price and gets more return on investment. So, to provide help to the decision makers to make reviews of the opinions data warehouse is used to collect all the views. Data warehouse stores it in database, filter responses and provide it to the companies through multidimensional models for deeper analysis (MoallaImen et al. (2017).

Benefits of Data Warehouse In Social Media

- It helps in getting updated information.
- Reviews helps in understanding needs of users.
- Right information is delivered at right time.
- It helps organizations in increasing return on investment.
- Efficiency in working methods can be improved.
- Data warehouse maintains the security of company and user data.
- It helps in scaling the business at a wider level.
- It helps in increasing quality of data as data warehouse structures the unstructured information of social media.
- Data warehouse helps in getting historical insights from social media about trends, likings of the buyers in earlier times.

Data collected in data warehouse is analyzed to determine patterns and their relationships. Different organizations make different plans and strategies according to the opinions of the buyers (Pushpam, Amali C. et al. (2017). Tourism industry has also gained a success by understanding reviews of the user. Different experiences of the users help in knowing different places of visit through social media. Data warehouse helps in storing all such opinions which will benefit all the tourism industry in creating strong databases (Nave, M et al. (2018).

Sports: data warehouse is widely used in the field of sports. It is one of the professional ways of organizing and analyzing different types of data. Large amount of information is generated relating to performance of the team members. Each step movement is stored and analyzed to understand and improve the performances of players. It also maintains budgets and profits so that exact information is provided to all administrators and everyone associated with the game. Multi-dimensional model of data warehouse helps in maintaining both transactional and operational mode of data in a logical manner which helps in making quicker and efficient decisions.

Data regarding different sports is integrated from different sources, extracted and gets loaded into data warehouse for deeper understandings of sports and its dash board. It further helps in reliable decisions as organization of data leads to effective results. Past records depict sports are always given importance. Earlier it was enjoyed as source of entertainment and now it has move more towards as business. Huge dollars are invested in sports and different players. Different Olympic games and many more events has made huge

investments and also provided support for job opportunities to many associated with it (Kauppi, K et al. (2013).

The advancements in technology have led to storage of information in the form of text, images, graphics, animation and video format. It has helped a lot in sports field as coaches and trainers can have deeper analyzes of data which assists them in training players. It is a visual game through which better training can be provided on multimedia databases. Users of the game can select any sports person of their interest for playing game. Data warehouse helps in extracting information for the users to take decisions from the current environment by applying data mining techniques. Relational model of data warehouse helps in representing information in star scheme and fact tables for quicker decisions and deeper analysis(Yan et al. (2015).

Uses of Data Warehouse In Sports

- It helps in the prediction of outcomes of the sports as it has deeper insights and organized way of deriving results.
- Data warehouse helps in analyzing the performances of his players as it keeps records of every movement of the player.
- It is of great help to the trainers to identify the areas in games which need to be improved.
- It helps trainers to take better decisions by considering different factors and also helps to determine budget and investment needed.

Data warehousing has provided assistance to the coach by giving historical status of different players along with their current performance. It guides the coaches to figure out strategies and tactics for training their wards. It is of great assistance for analyzers to take decisions. The statistics are easily generated according to the performance level of sportsperson and also provides digitized for keeping records of tournament.

Banks: Banks are the organizations which maintain a large database of customers. They need to maintain both historical and current data of their customers. Today all banks are operating in a digital world and they need to maintain tremendous amount of data. Due to huge competition in banks, they need strategies and analytics to process their vast amount of data to provide optimize services to their customers.

Banks need data warehouse to maintain information at a central core and helps management in taking decisions. It is one of the modern ways to measure the performance of organizations. It extracts information from organization's internal database(Stolba N. et al. (2005). Banks gives the importance to the management of customer relationship for retaining the customers for longer period. Data warehouse has helped a lot in managing customer relationships in banks. It helps in providing customer's geographic information, transactions committed and status of profitability relationship(Onut S. et al. (2008).

The reliability of banks on data warehouse has enhanced for assessing risk, managing customers, generating reports, analyzing historical data, management of compliances of customers. Different banks need to integrate information regarding bank loans, deposits,

financial condition so that better delivery services can be provided. Business intelligence on the data warehouse helps managers of all levels to take effective decisions. This strong knowledge of databases helps banks to survive easily in competitive environment(Rao, G. et al. (2011).

Importance Of Data Warehouse In Banking

- Maintaining Customers- data warehouse helps in retaining customers as complete record of customers is stored and maintained. It maintains all historical and current data along with different segments of customers and profitability.
- Risk Management- banks need to maintain factual data so that accurate decisions can be taken. Decisions based on correct and accurate data help to reduce the level of risk.
- Fraud Detection- banks are at the great risk of fraud. So, to timely identify and remove these malicious thefts is very important for banks. Data warehouse maintains all the information in an integrated way and further mining techniques on integrated data help to reduce fraud.
- Performance Indicators- banks data warehouse not only maintains current data but also historical records which help in comparing performance with previous years. So, it helps in analyzing the performance of banks.
- Feedback- it helps banks in getting proper feedback about the bank's operational environments, customers, financial performance and profitability status.

Banking sector has attained many advantages from data warehouse. Banks have tried to improve its technical sector so that benefits like accuracy, efficiency, enhancements in day-to-day performance can be availed. All these factors help in improving decision making for enhancing the conduct of banking activities. Banking sector is trying to remove all hindrances like technology limitation, staff effectiveness, vendor support so that it should be adopted with full advantage(Intrapariot, A. et al. (1998). So, banks need to adopt new technologies to attain the loyalty of their customers, profitability in their businesses, quick decisions and lowering the level of risk. Data warehouse helps in collection of this unstructured data to the normalized data to handle all the queries relating to banks and helps in monitoring the performances.

CHALLENGES OF DATA WAREHOUSE

- Technology Limitations- data is gathered from different sources. There is availability of many tools for handling data but there is complexity in managing data from different platforms and integrating at a single place.
- Quality of data- It is important to manage accurate data as all decisions are based on it. But many front-end tools do not gather complete information which hampers the effectiveness of data warehouse.
- Implementation complexity- there is limitation in installation and setup of data warehouse. Requirement of hardware, software, experts and operational execution complexities.

- Lack of expertise- there is a need of skillful persons in the implementation of data warehouse who has complete knowledge of technical skills for its processing.
- Required effort, cost and time- implementation of data warehouse requires proper time, investment and experts.
- Lack of flexibility- today's era demand flexibility in organizations to adapt according to the changing needs but it is difficult to implement in data warehouse.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this paper we discuss about the importance of data warehouse in different application areas. Data Warehouse has provided a great support in many organizations by managing data from different sources. It structures information and helps organization in taking effective and efficient decisions. The paper also discusses about the architecture of data warehouse and provides detailed view from different perspectives. The working of many areas which includes education, sports, health, manufacturing, and business is effectively depended upon data warehouse for their smooth conduct. But for future work needs to be done on improving technology so that data warehouse helps organizations in the smooth conduct and also effective mining techniques helps in taking best decisions.

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